

USING GESTURES AND BODY LANGUAGE IN EFL CLASSES

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Abstract:

This abstract intends to highlight the relevance of gestures and body language in EFL classes, stressing the benefits and practical implications for educators. The incorporation of nonverbal communication in EFL training has been shown to improve learners' comprehension, engagement and cultural understanding.

Key words: gestures, body language, EFL classes, emotional expressions, facial expressions, communication

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/hab47a40>

In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms, effective communication goes beyond words. Integrating gestures and body language can significantly enhance the learning experience for students, regardless of their proficiency level. Here's how incorporating gestures and body language can benefit EFL classes. Classroom teaching, as well as all know is a type of communicative engagement between teachers and students. Aside from the students' subjective reason teachers are also to blame for this problem. Teachers must hard work to capture and maintain students' attention in order to engage them in learning. In some circumstances, nonverbal communication is more crucial than verbal communication in interactions between teachers and students. As well known, loudness, speed and tone of voice will directly stimulate the pupils' response. Human body language as a form of nonverbal communication that includes gestures and facial emotions, frequently utilized to communicate in a variety of situation.

Body language plays an important part in education, not only in EFL classes but also in forming students' personalities. Students frequently revere their teachers and at time subconsciously copy their words and gestures. As a result, teachers must accurately grasp body language and learn the methods and concepts of body language. As English teachers in modern era, must use new teaching techniques to help students learn the foreign language. Using gestures and body language during EFL classes extremely useful and interesting for students.

The EFL is - English as a Foreign Language. The EFL classroom is a learning and using English as an additional language in a non-English speaking country. In an EFL classroom, the primary goal is to help students develop proficiency in English, encompassing skills in reading, writing, listening and speaking. EFL classes includes short summer schools or courses in an English-speaking country, such as the UK, USA. There are some aspects for EFL classes;

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Language Acquisition: In EFL classes, there is a strong emphasis on learning language skills during lessons and practice.

Cultural Context: In EFL classes, teaching the culture of English speaking countries is important. Because students know the country and they are studying it customs and traditions.

Gestures are physical expressive movements used to convey ideas, feelings or messages that cannot be expressed verbally. They are commonly used in everyday communication to supplement or reinforce speech. Gestures can be used to support language learning.

Visual clarity: Gestures can help illustrate the meaning of words or sentences, giving learners a visual representation to aid comprehension.

Emotional expressions: Gestures can be used to express emotions or feelings, aiding in the reinforcements of the meaning of words or concepts.

Eye contact

Maintaining appropriate eye contact is essential in any setting. Emotions and expectations vary. Individual eye contact with each student throughout a class indicates the teacher's focus and excitement.

Facial expressions

Using facial expressions to teach is a very effective method in EFL classes. After asking a question to the students, if they give a correct answer, react with a smile on your face. If they give an incorrect answer, raise your eyebrows to show surprise. This helps students grasp the intended meaning more accurately. All three types of nonverbal facial communication are used in the classroom. However, the third type, facial markers is the focus of this review. Aside from speech, these flexing expressions are the primary basis for determining an identity. Some of the smallest bodily parts are involved in facial emotions. However, their impact in the classroom is significant. The instructor conveys more whether consciously or unintentionally, by his or her facial expressions than by any other factor other means.

Meaningful gestures

In EFL classes, this method is used for to learn and remember a new words by associating it with a specific gesture and keeping it in long-term memory. For example, if we take the word "jumping" its meaning by moving upward. Discovered numerous methods for boosting gesture in the classroom. Try to embrace as much of the audience as possible by gesticulating with both arms and hands. Keep your hands out in front, not in your pockets working for you. Take notes in your non-dominant hand. Use motions that are proportional to the size of the audience. The movements should be more broad and severe as the audience size increase.

Mimicing

This is one of the best ways. Watch native English speakers video and pay attention how to use their hands or emotions

Role-playing

In role-playing dialogues with a partner use gestures and body language. This is can help you communication skills and improve your fluency.

Posture

From the distance, posture can assist express an overall internal message. Before words are said, one may read and forecast an individual's mood. Posture and eye contact are utilized to communicate attitudes, status, affective moods, approval, deception, warmth and other classroom interaction factors.

Vocal Intonation

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Vocal intonations, also known as paralanguage, encompass characteristic such as loudness, pace, pitch, tone and pronunciation, in order to work as an to be an effective speaker, one must capture the listener's interest though the manner in which one communicates.

In conclusion, gestures and body language play a crucial role in enhancing English language learning in EFL classrooms. By incorporating these non-verbal communication tools into lesson plans, teachers can create a more immersive, engaging, and effective learning environment for their students.

We can see that body language and gestures are beneficial to English instruction. And, if we want to improve the quality of education, we must eliminate typical boredom and monotony. The English classroom will be transformed into a stage for both professors and students. Teachers should teach their students in a comfortable environment. Body language can be a useful tool for enhancing students' imaginations and assisting teachers in more vividly expressing their ideas and language points. And through body language they can express some linguistic connotations that are difficult to express verbally. Body language can improve the teaching quality in EFL classes. A number of students can enjoy an active atmosphere of English learning instead of a boring and serious one. In EFL classes should be active and relaxed. Sometimes gestures and body language are widely used to convey ideas during verbal conversation. Using gestures and body language in EFL classes extremely useful and interesting for students.

References:

- [1]. Gladis, Stephen D (1985) *Notes are Not Enough . Training and Development Journal, August, 35-38*
- [2]. Kansas State University, Physics Department, *Introduction in Nonverbal communication (n.d.)/ Retreived October 16,2003 from <http://www.phys.ksu.edu/~zhrepic/gened/nonverbalcom/non-verbalcom.htm>*
- [3]. White, Gayle-Webb(2000). *Non-verbal Communications: key to improved teacher effectiveness. The Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin, 66(4), 12-16*